

Deliverable

D5.1 Monitoring and Evaluation Concept

Project	PRO-Ethics – Participatory real life experiments in research and innovation funding organisations on ethics
Project Acronym	PRO-Ethics
Project Number	872441
Deliverable:	D5.1
Submission Date:	31.10.2020
Resubmission Date:	11.11.2021
Responsible Author(s)	Dorothea Sturn, Stefanie Schuerz

Document Control Sheet

Work Package Number	WP5
Work Package Title	Synthesis – Ethics framework and practical guidelines
Task Number	T5.1
Task Title	Monitoring and Evaluation Concept
Deliverable Number	D5.1
Deliverable Title	Monitoring and Evaluation Concept
File name	D5.1_Monitoring and Evaluation Concept_update
Number of pages	25
Dissemination level	Public
Main author	Dorothea Sturn
Contributors	Stefanie Schuerz
Quality Assurance	Klaus Schuch, Kristoffer Rekve, Stefanie Schuerz

Versioning and Contribution History

Version	Date	Author/Editor	Co-Author	Notes
_v00	12.10.2020	Dorothea Sturn		First draft
_v01	23.10.2020	Klaus Schuch, Kristoffer Rekve		Feedback, internal and partner review
_v02	28.10.2020	Dorothea Sturn		Incorporation of feedback
_final	31.10.2020	Stefanie Schuerz	Dorothea Sturn	Editing and finalisation
_update	11.11.2021	Dorothea Sturn	Stefanie Schuerz	Review according to the review report

Table of Contents

1. Executive Summary	6
2. Introduction	7
2.1 <i>Criteria for and Development of the Monitoring and Evaluation Concept</i>	7
3. PART A: General Rules and Standards	9
3.1 <i>Terms of Reference (ToR)</i>	9
3.1.1 Transformative change	9
3.1.2 Gender	9
3.1.3 Open Science	9
3.1.4 Ethics	9
3.1.5 Quality assurance	10
3.2 <i>Theory of Change</i>	10
3.3 <i>Suggestions for Evaluation Methods</i>	11
3.4 <i>Timing</i>	12
4. PART B: Concrete Template (Minimum elements)	13
4.1 <i>A Simple Schedule for the Evaluation</i>	13
4.2 <i>Evaluation Questions and Indicators</i>	14
5. PART C: Toolbox	17
5.1 <i>Evaluation Questions</i>	17
5.1.1 Questions addressing the participants	17
5.1.2 Questions addressing the RDI agents	18
5.1.3 Questions concerning project and process management	19
5.2 <i>Outputs and Outcomes</i>	19
5.3 <i>Data and Indicators to be Collected in the Course of Monitoring</i>	20
5.4 <i>MoRRI indicators</i>	21
6. References	24
List of Figures and Tables	25

1. Executive Summary

The present deliverable is the main output of Task 5.1, which entails the development of a Monitoring and Evaluation Concept. This concept is aimed specifically at the eleven Pilot cases of the PRO-Ethics project, which in turn serve as real live experiments of participatory approaches in research and innovation funding. The pilots are organised in two phases, intended to maximise the possible impact of the project. To this end, the four ongoing Phase I Pilot Cases are reviewed and the learnings applied to create the seven Phase II Pilot Cases. D5.1 Monitoring and Evaluation Concept thus serves to monitor and evaluate the present Pilots, as well as to create, monitor, and evaluate the new Pilots of Phase II. Beyond the confines of the PRO-Ethics project, the Monitoring and Evaluation Concept should also be applicable outside the project consortium in other programmes and processes with participatory elements. Because of this, the present Concept aims for a rather abstract approach to monitoring and evaluation, to ensure broad applicability.

This aim is well-served by the fact that the Pilot Cases of PRO-Ethics are very different from one other. Using them as a basis, the present Monitoring and Evaluation Concept thus attempts to enable broad applicability, while at the same time allowing for a certain comparability of the individual pilots.

With this logic in mind, the present deliverable is structured as follows:

- ▶ In a first part of the concept (Part A) general rules and procedures are explained that research funding organisations (RFOs) have to consider when designing their individual evaluation concept. It contains the formulation of Terms of Reference (ToR), an example of how the intervention logic can be illustrated with a Theory of Change (ToC) approach, suggestions for evaluation methods, as well as a time schedule.
- ▶ A second part (Part B) defines a very concise evaluation concept which is binding for all PRO-Ethics partners. Firstly, it provides a simple evaluation plan with a flow chart and, secondly, it formulates evaluation questions and indicators along four central dimensions: Motivation and Leanings, Ethics and Integrity, Gender and Equality as well as the Intensity of the Participants' involvement
- ▶ Finally, a third part (Part C) provides a toolbox from which RFOs can select those elements that seem useful to their individual concept. This toolbox consists of further evaluation questions, outputs and outcomes at various levels as well as data and indicators (both general ones and MoRRI indicators).

In this way, an attempt is made to adapt the concepts to the individual pilots and evaluation practices of the different RFOs on the one hand, and to create a comparable basis for all pilots on the other. Finally, in conjunction with the "Templates for Reporting and Assessment" (D3.1) and the "Reports on Pilot I results" (D2.1), the present deliverable will lay the foundation for a comprehensive analysis and evaluation of the pilots and provide important input for the first Ethics framework in T1.4.

2. Introduction

The present D5.1 Monitoring and Evaluation Concept is intended to help the eight RFO partners participating in the PRO-Ethics project to monitor and evaluate their Pilot Cases. Subsequently, other programmes and processes with participatory elements should be able to work with the concept as well. Since the Pilots are very distinct, each individual case requires adaptation to meet both the specificities of the Pilot Cases and the RFOs' internal monitoring and evaluation practices.

The concept is divided into three parts:

- ▶ Part A describes general rules and standards to be considered when designing evaluations.
- ▶ Part B provides a short structure and formulates a concrete proposal as to which elements the evaluation should contain at the very minimum.
- ▶ Part C offers a kind of toolbox with examples and further material that can be used if appropriate.

Ideally, evaluation considerations should already be reflected in the design of a pilot, and every RFO should consider from the outset what scope the evaluation should have. This includes the required monitoring data, the exact time schedule and the criteria for awarding the evaluation. If an RFO plans to carry out similar participatory processes or programmes in the future, it is worthwhile to outsource the evaluation with carefully formulated Terms of Reference (TOR). Otherwise, the evaluation can also be carried out internally or as a self-evaluation.

The ToR need to detail the scope of the evaluation, the evaluation questions, as well as the processes and conditions of the evaluation. The requested methods (if any) and specific indicators must also be adapted to the specificities of each case. In addition to the evaluation practices of the individual RFOs, the participants involved (citizens, users, etc.), the ethical dimensions covered, the content and aims of the pilot (research, innovation, development), as well as the intensity and type of participation also play a role here.

The division of this deliverable into the proposed three parts attempts to do justice to the diversity of the pilots. While the evaluation processes must be adapted to the specifics of each pilot, Part B is intended to provide a framework that is binding for all. Therefore, this part defines the mandatory minimum elements of each evaluation. Part A provides general rules and precedes this mandatory part. In order to provide additional material for those pilots planning a particularly ambitious evaluation design, the toolbox in Part C offers evaluation questions, material and indicators that can be used additionally if needed.

2.1 Criteria for and Development of the Monitoring and Evaluation Concept

The evaluation questions found in Part B and Part C of this document were developed through an interactive process in the following manner:

First, relevant literature (Kohlweg (2019) Schaefer, Kieslinger (2016)) served to organize the various questions into the three central categories of participants, researchers and society. Since in PRO-Ethics we address innovators from companies and research institutions rather than basic researchers, the term RDI agents was applied instead of researchers, following the terminology already developed in D3.1.

Based on this outline, the RFO partners formulated questions that were of particular relevance in their specific contexts of the pilots and discussed these questions together. They also took into account that the participatory activities in the pilots are less about classic citizen science projects involving lay people in research projects and more often about participation in evaluation, selection, and decision-making processes or strategic planning by the RFOs.

Finally, the collected questions were cleaned from redundancies and structured. A distinction was made between questions that should be used in every case (Part B) and those that can be used additionally in individual pilots (Part C).

The following questions guided the process of developing a concept for monitoring and evaluation:

- ▶ How could the RFO partners define the goals of their pilots? What would constitute success in their implementation?
- ▶ How should participatory activities in the pilots to be evaluated? How could success be measured?
- ▶ How did participants perceive the various activities they took part in? Were they satisfied with the process and their role in it?
- ▶ Were the different target groups (participants, RDI agents, RFOs) adequately addressed?
- ▶ Can the evaluation approach be applied to other participatory processes or programs within the research funding organisations and beyond?

Broadly speaking, the concept was designed to meet four aims:

- ▶ **Assessment of target achievement:** The questions are intended to provide information on the extent to which the individual pilots have achieved their targets.
- ▶ **Efficiency and effectiveness:** The questions are also intended to assess the efficiency and effectiveness of the processes used.
- ▶ **Satisfaction of the actors involved:** All actors involved should be predominantly satisfied with the interactive activities and processes. This includes that they are well informed about all events and know their rights and obligations.
- ▶ **Transferability to other programmes or activities:** The questions developed should also be applicable in other contexts.

3. PART A: General Rules and Standards

3.1 Terms of Reference (ToR)

Each evaluation must be planned carefully: Objectives, purpose, scope, content, evaluation questions as well as the budget and schedule should be formulated clearly in the ToR. The ToR are a

“written document presenting the purpose and scope of the evaluation, the methods to be used, the standards against which performance is to be assessed or analyses are to be conducted, the resources and time allocated, and reporting requirements” (OECD 2009, p. 36)

In the course of the implementation of Pilot II (T2.4), the PRO-Ethics RFO partners will decide how monitoring and evaluation will be carried out in each Pilot II Case. If possible, the evaluation itself should also include participatory elements such as the involvement of citizens, user groups, patients or whatever is relevant for the specific pilot case.

The evaluation plan should take into account the following issues (see e.g.: Edler et al. 2012, Kohlweg 2018):

3.1.1 Transformative change

Against the background of major global and social challenges, the needs of a goal-oriented, transformative change in RDI (research, development and innovation) systems should be considered (see e.g. Scot et al. 2018). All PRO-Ethics Pilots include transformative elements as they are oriented towards concrete social and societal problems, catalyse concrete processes of change, and involve various actors in the research process.

3.1.2 Gender

Gender aspects should be considered at every step of the evaluation, and by all those involved. In the event that there is no gender dimension apparent in the evaluation object, this should also be indicated and explained. Gender-specific data are to be collected, evaluated and interpreted. Contexts (concepts, strategies, policy documents, programme documents, interventions, etc.) and any information gathered are analysed for gender-specific differences and interpreted in this light.

3.1.3 Open Science

The evaluation process, its findings, and the subsequent recommendations should be conducted and completed in a manner that is transparent and accountable for all those involved and affected. This also requires open access to evaluation findings and their publication.

3.1.4 Ethics

All persons involved in or affected by an evaluation should be treated with respect and fairness. Evaluations must be planned and conducted in a manner that protects an individual’s rights, privacy and dignity. Sensitive data may not be used without consent, and should not be traceable to their source.

It is imperative that ethical issues are considered during the formulation of the evaluation plan. Ethical considerations include:

- ▶ Informed consent

- ▶ Voluntary participation
- ▶ Confidentiality
- ▶ Anonymity

3.1.5 Quality assurance

Quality assurance should take place throughout the evaluation process. Quality requirements should be formulated in advance, and data and information systematically checked for errors.

3.2 Theory of Change

The first step for each evaluation is to illustrate the intervention logic of the Pilot Case in question. To this end, it must be clarified:

- ▶ What resources are being used?
- ▶ What activities are being undertaken?
- ▶ What are the immediate outputs?
- ▶ What intermediate outcomes and what long-term impacts (including unintended impacts) are to be expected from the intervention?

A Theory of Change (ToC) is a logical deduction for an intervention pathway, starting with high level objectives and rationales about the expected changes that policy interventions should trigger or enforce, which are then broken down into specific activities, measures and outputs that are supposed to drive the change. A ToC asks what will have changed or what changes will have occurred due to policy interventions. Thus, the ToC approach focuses primarily on the tangible (sequence of) outcomes/results of an intervention or a portfolio of interventions, and not just on the overall objectives. The quality of a ToC can be approximated by *plausibility* (i.e. the logic of the outcome pathways), the *feasibility* (i.e. can the proposed interventions realistically achieve the expected outcomes and impact) and *testability* (which refers broadly to the indicators). In a further step, an evaluation could track whether these expected outcomes could have been actually produced (or not).

The construction of a Theory of Change is intended to be an interactive process in which selected stakeholders, programme owners, and agencies (in case the owner differs from the agency) should be involved. The authors of the present D5.1 Monitoring and Evaluation Concept support these processes on demand. The following picture shows examples of inputs, processes, outputs, outcomes and impacts.

Figure 1: Example of a Theory of Change

3.3 Suggestions for Evaluation Methods

The choice of methods depends on the evaluation questions posed by the ToR, the intended scope of the evaluation and the available data. It is recommended to allow the evaluators a certain degree of freedom and not to list the methods completely in the ToR.

The various evaluations which will be carried out in the course of PRO-Ethics should be methodologically diverse. Depending on the objectives, purpose and scope of the evaluation, various quantitative and qualitative methods could be used. In any case, evaluators should make use of any existing and valid monitoring data in order to avoid duplicated data collection in the evaluation process. The selection of data and methods of data collection and analysis are derived from the information requested in the evaluation questions. Scientific principles of empirical research must be taken into account when collecting, analysing and interpreting data.

The various strengths and weaknesses of the methods used should be clarified as needed, and combined according to the principle of complementarity (the strengths of one approach largely balances the weaknesses of other approaches). Methods may be qualitative or quantitative, and can include for instance:

- ▶ case studies
- ▶ surveys
- ▶ focus groups
- ▶ interviews

-
- ▶ international comparisons
 - ▶ statistical analysis

Our proposal in section B requires at least simple descriptive statistics, presentation and interpretation of monitoring data as well as the analysis of primary data (collected through surveys, focus groups, interviews).

3.4 Timing

While monitoring is ongoing throughout the participatory process, there are various options for evaluation: This can be carried out either accompanying or ex-post. In an ex-post evaluation, the choice of the ideal time is a complex matter: Directly after the end of a project or process, the people involved are usually easily accessible and the events are still fresh in the participants' minds. On the other hand, some effects of the intervention appear a long time afterwards. Therefore, it is recommended that an evaluation be conducted in several rounds over a longer period of time, which, however, means a considerable amount of additional time and effort.

Our proposal in Part B therefore contains a pragmatic compromise of ex-post evaluation about two to three years after the end of the intervention.

4. PART B: Concrete Template (Minimum elements)

4.1 A Simple Schedule for the Evaluation

This part of the Monitoring and Evaluation Concept formulates a simple proposal for evaluation. It should be conducted as proposed by all RFO partners participating in PRO-Ethics, in order to ensure comparability between the different Pilot Cases. Each evaluation should be carried out at the very minimum in one iteration ex-post (two to three years after the intervention), according to the following plan:

- ▶ Decision whether the evaluation should be contracted out to professional evaluators or carried out internally
- ▶ Formulation of the Terms of Reference (ToR, see page 8) also in the case of an internal evaluation). These should at least contain: The objective of the intervention, the planning of a Theory of Change (ToC, see page 9), the evaluation questions, the methods (or the invitation to the evaluators to present a methodological concept), a timetable including milestones (see page 11), and the required qualifications of the evaluators.
- ▶ Call for tender for the Terms of References and award of the evaluation (or internal award)
- ▶ Kick-off meeting with the evaluators
- ▶ Implementation of the evaluation (elements are at the minimum: data analysis, primary data collection, analysis and interpretation, conclusions and recommendations)
- ▶ Publication and presentation of the results
- ▶ Formulation of the resulting needs for change (by the RFO in charge)

The following figure shows the evaluation schedule

Figure 2: Evaluation Plan

Each evaluation should cover the following four dimensions:

- ▶ Motivation and Learnings: Evaluation of the motives for participation and the knowledge produced throughout the process

- ▶ Ethics and Integrity: Evaluation of the ethical aspects of the project, such as inclusion, data management, project design and resources
- ▶ Gender and Equality: Evaluation of diverse mechanism of inequality in RDI (research, development, innovation)
- ▶ Intensity of Involvement: Evaluation of the intensity of the collaboration between participants¹ and RDI agents² (participation, engagement or involvement)³

4.2 Evaluation Questions and Indicators

The evaluation questions are at the very centre of each evaluation. All planning and the selection of appropriate methods should be based on the questions the evaluators are supposed to answer. The suggested questions in this section are grouped under the above mentioned dimensions and address both participants and RDI agents.

Figure 3: Four dimensions of evaluation

In the following, central questions and indicators are assigned to these four dimensions. Further questions, indicators and evaluation elements can be found in Part C.

¹ Participants are defined as persons who take part in engagement processes. These persons might be: Citizens (without a specific interest in the case), (end-) users (with a specific interest in the results), and stakeholders including non-traditional stakeholders like NGOs (with specific knowledge and/or specific interest). Furthermore, participants can both be individuals or representatives of institutions or groups and may include vulnerable groups such as patients, children, and older adults. In each Pilot Case the kind of participating individuals or groups should be carefully described (see also D3.1).

² RDI agents include researchers in higher education institutions (HEIs) and research performing organisations as well as researchers, developers and innovators in enterprises, NGOs and public bodies. As in the case of “participants”, “RDI agents” might be individuals (e.g. individual researchers) or institutions/institutional delegates (e.g. universities or firms) (see also D3.1).

³ Since Arnstein’s “Ladder of Citizen Participation” in 1969, a number of approaches which structure the type and intensity of citizens’ involvement can be witnessed (e.g. Wiggins & Crownstow (2011), Prainsack (2014), Schaefer & Kieslinger (2016)).

Dimensions / Target group	Participants	RDI agents
Motivation and Learnings: Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ What are the motives for participating? ▶ Does the project or process contribute to a better understanding of RDI? ▶ Has the project or process changed the personal career or professional orientation? ▶ Has the perception of/view on RDI changed? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ What are the motives for participating? ▶ Have new skills been developed or used? ▶ How important is the project or process to the careers of the RDI agents involved? ▶ Has the project or process changed the perception of one's own role as a researcher?
Motivation and Learnings: Indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Number of participants included ▶ Number of participants with positive feedback ▶ Number of participants who have been involved in the participatory process until the end 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Number of RDI agents included ▶ Number of RDI agents with positive feedback ▶ New skills and knowledge reported in the feedback forms
Ethics and Integrity: Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Were the participants treated fairly and with respect? ▶ Did they receive an adequate compensation for their effort? ▶ Were the results communicated to participants? ▶ Were the participants acknowledged as contributors? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Has the project or process changed the handling of ethical questions or research integrity? ▶ Was there any improvement?
Ethics and Integrity: Indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Number of mentions of participants as contributors ▶ Number of participatory processes or projects with fully completed consent forms ▶ Number of participatory processes or projects for which the participants have received compensation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Number of outputs that comply with the rules of good scientific practice ▶ Number of data collected and stored according to the FAIR principles⁴
Intensity of Participants' Involvement: Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Participation: Do the participants take part in research and innovation studies or activities (e.g. complete questionnaires)? ▶ Engagement: Do the participants receive information and knowledge about research and innovation activities (e.g. via science festivals)? ▶ Involvement: Are the participants actively involved in research and innovation (e.g. via co-creation approaches or as co-applicants)? 	
Intensity of Participants' Involvement: Indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Number of projects or processes with participation ▶ Number of projects or processes with engagement ▶ Number of projects or processes with involvement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Number of projects or processes with participation ▶ Number of projects or processes with engagement ▶ Number of projects or processes with involvement

Table 1: Evaluation questions and indicators

In addition to these central content dimensions, it can also be helpful to evaluate the quality of project and process management on the part of RFOs. However, as this is difficult to do in internal

⁴ The FAIR Data Principles are a set of guiding principles in order to make data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (Wilkinson et al., 2016)

evaluations, evaluation questions of this type should be voluntary. Exemplary questions can therefore be found in Part C.

5. PART C: Toolbox

After Part B of the Monitoring and Evaluation Concept has defined processes, evaluation questions and indicators that should be covered on a mandatory basis by all RFOs, Part C provides additional material that can be used as a supplement.

The toolbox contains an extended list of evaluation questions that have been discussed together with the RFOs but cannot be usefully applied in all pilots. These additional questions can be referred to if needed. Furthermore, outputs and outcomes for participants, RDI agents and society are addressed, which were discursively tackled in the workshops and discussions during the development of D3.1 (especially in the cross-learning workshop in June 2020). The inputs from the RFOs were systematised and supplemented with references from the literature (cf. e.g. Brest, P. (2010), Kohlweg, K. (2019) Schaefer, T. & Kieslinger, B. (2016)). Finally, MoRRI indicators may be additionally relevant. Therefore, a table of MoRRI indicators (see European Commission (2018a) and (2018b)) is added to the toolbox and an assessment is made of which indicators are meaningful for PRO-Ethics.

5.1 Evaluation Questions

The evaluation questions listed here cover all questions listed in Part B and list a few more, adhering to the same overall structure. In addition, there are questions that address RDI institutions and some questions that concern project and process management.

5.1.1 Questions addressing the participants

Motivation and Learnings

- ▶ What are the motives for participating?
- ▶ Does the project or process contribute to a better understanding of RDI?
- ▶ Are there any insights in terms of content and method?
- ▶ Has the project or process changed the personal career or professional orientation?
- ▶ Has the perception of/view on RDI changed?
- ▶ Were the RDI agents satisfied with the processes, the communication, the results?
- ▶ How far did the project achieve its scientific and innovative objectives (qualitatively and quantitatively)?
- ▶ Have new questions or research needs arisen from the project?
- ▶ Are there any follow-up projects planned? Are there any further projects planned on similar issues?
- ▶ What influence does the type of cooperation have on the gaining of knowledge?

Ethics and Integrity

- ▶ Were the participants treated fairly and with respect?
- ▶ Did they receive an adequate compensation for their effort?
- ▶ Were the results communicated to participants?
- ▶ Were the participants acknowledged as contributors?

Gender and Equality

- ▶ Were participants selected in a gender sensitive way?
- ▶ Did both genders have adequate access to the processes and results?
- ▶ Were negative and pervasive stereotypes and discriminatory processes/attitudes tackled?

- ▶ Have gender-relevant aspects of research or innovation been addressed?
- ▶ Were different dimension of social inequality and diversity taken into account during the research or innovation process (including the selection process)?
- ▶ Were questions of power structures and social inequality during the research or innovation process adequately addressed?

Intensity of the Participants' Involvement

- ▶ Participation: Do the participants take part in research and innovation studies (e.g. complete questionnaires)?
- ▶ Engagement: Do the participants receive information and knowledge about research and innovation activities (e.g. via science festivals)?
- ▶ Involvement: Are the participants actively involved in research and innovation (e.g. via co-creation approaches or as co-applicants)?

5.1.2 Questions addressing the RDI agents

Motivation and Learnings

- ▶ What are the motives for participating?
- ▶ What has been learned through the project?
- ▶ Have new skills been developed or used?
- ▶ How important is the project or process to the careers of the RDI agents involved?
- ▶ Has the project or process changed the perception of one's own role as a researcher?

Ethics and Integrity

- ▶ Has the project or process changed the handling of ethical questions or research integrity?
- ▶ Was there any improvement regarding said handling?

Gender and Equality

- ▶ Was gender inequality addressed in the proposal evaluation process?
- ▶ Were the diverse mechanisms of inequality in R&I tackled?
- ▶ Did both genders have adequate access to the processes and results?
- ▶ Were negative and pervasive stereotypes and discriminatory processes/attitudes tackled?
- ▶ Have gender-relevant aspects of research or innovation been addressed?
- ▶ Were questions of power structures and social inequality during the research process adequately addressed?

RDI Institutions

- ▶ What is the importance of the project or process for the research institutions and firms involved?
- ▶ Is there a process of structural change due to the project (e.g. new working groups)?
- ▶ Have cooperations with citizens or civil society organisations been established? Are these cooperations sustainable? Will these cooperations continue after the end of the project?
- ▶ What hurdles and challenges were met in the course of the project?
- ▶ Do the results of the project feed into other activities or projects?
- ▶ Are there any new rules and guidelines concerning research ethics as a result of the project or process?

5.1.3 Questions concerning project and process management

- ▶ Does the RFO provide proper support for participatory projects and processes?
- ▶ Are both the participants and the RDI agents adequately informed and supported?
- ▶ Are the processes properly timed? Is sufficient time allowed for the individual work steps?
- ▶ How well and efficiently does communication with the RFO work?
- ▶ Are the processes clearly and comprehensibly designed?
- ▶ Are the formats adapted to the target groups?

5.2 Outputs and Outcomes

Both for the preparation of a ToC and for raising awareness of the impacts of participatory projects and processes, it can be helpful to define the outputs and expected outcomes more precisely.

The following section defines outputs and outcomes at the levels of:

- ▶ Participants
- ▶ RDI agents
- ▶ Society (including the socio/economic/ecological system)

A concretisation for each individual Pilot Case must be made. The outputs and outcomes are partly taken from D3.1 “Template for Reporting and Assessment” in order to ensure the compatibility between reporting, monitoring and evaluation. “Enhanced scientific literacy” was removed because the term is too complex to ask participants and there is some overlap with the category “deeper and broader understanding”. In the course of the evaluation, the respective parties should be asked whether the outputs, outcomes and impacts were achieved, and if so to what extent. When planning and implementing the evaluation, it must be taken into account that outcomes and especially impacts may occur only years after the finalisation of the projects/Pilots. Furthermore, many outcomes and impacts might not be attributed to a single project but are the result of various experiences and projects.

Level	Outputs	Expected Outcomes
Participants (citizens)	Interest in RDI was increased	Personal development
	Access to RDI, deeper and broader understanding	Behaviour change
	A greater say in and commitment to RDI matters	Enhanced motivation
	Contribution to better solutions (innovative product and/or service)	
	Improved Skills and gained knowledge	
Awareness of societal structures of power and inequity	Higher commitment to improving societal equity	
RDI agents (researchers)	New discoveries and results, new RDI questions	Networks and ecosystems of participation
	Better solutions that meet the needs and wishes	Enhanced credibility of and trust in science and

	of the users/target group	research
	Better understanding of the market	
	Deeper investigation of research questions, on a much larger scale	Behaviour change due to the consideration of societal impacts
	Made research more accessible to a wider audience and increasing its reach	Higher commitment to improving societal equity
	Awareness of societal structures of power and inequity was raised	
	Respectful and equitable cooperation with diverse research participants	
Society (socio/economic/ecological system)		Higher societal trust in RDI
		Society-relevant research questions and topics
		Permeability and transparency at the interface of research, innovation and wider publics
		Closing cultural divides by elevating societal communication structures between diverse groups of actors

Table 2: Outputs and Outcomes at various levels

5.3 Data and Indicators to be Collected in the Course of Monitoring

The monitoring system of the agencies involved in the Pilot Cases should record all relevant process and output data in a simple, systematic and gender-sensitive manner. Gathered data are used partly for monitoring the (achievement of) content as well as financial aspects of a project. Monitoring data provides evaluators with a clear picture of the funded projects under certain interventions and schemes. Monitoring helps to improve the data quality of the evaluation, avoids duplication of efforts and reduces the work of data collection. Since all PRO-Ethics Pilots report their cases according to D3.1 (“Templates for Reporting and Assessment”), a common core data set for monitoring by the agencies is already available and should be used for evaluation purposes as well.

Level	Data
Participants (citizens)	Amount of data collected with the help of citizens
	Total number of citizens/users/stakeholders included
	Number of participatory events
	Number of participants at each event
	Specific skills and knowledge participants bring to the table
	Socio-economic data (age, gender, etc.)

RDI agents (researchers)		Number of disciplines involved in the project
		Number of collaborations with project partners
		Number of papers published
		Number of citations
		Number of grants
		Number of patents
Society (socio/economic/ecological system)		Follow-up by participants after end of activities
		Further commitments
		Civic engagement

Table 3: Suggestions for Monitoring data

Besides these quite general data, some of the MoRRI indicators⁵ (see European Commission 2018a and 2018b) might be of interest in the context of the monitoring. This is particularly important where the intervention contributes to key RRI dimensions, namely Gender, Public Engagement, Ethics, and Governance. A full list of indicators can be found below.

5.4 MoRRI indicators

The following table lists some MoRRI indicators which may be of interest in the context of PRO-Ethics. The necessary data is either collected in the project or is derived from secondary statistics. The secondary statistical indicators can be used for comparison purposes or as benchmarks. Some descriptions of the indicators were slightly adapted to the wording and content of PRO-Ethics. Namely, instead of “researchers” the term “RDI agent” is used, and instead of “research” the term “research and innovation” or “RDI” (research, development, innovation) was used.

The below table contains not just the MoRRI indicators, but also a mention of data sources as well as the relevance each indicator has for the PRO-Ethics project. This rating remains at a rather general level concerning all Pilot Cases. This means some of the Pilot Cases might assess the relative relevance of the indicator differently. Here, again, individual adaptations are necessary.

RRI dimension	Indicator	Description	Data Source	Relevance for PRO-Ethics
Gender Equality	GE1	Share of RDI agents with gender equality plans	primary	high
	GE2	Share of female researchers by sector	Eurostat	low
	GE3	Share of RDI agents promoting gender content in research and innovation	primary	high

⁵ The MoRRI project (2014-2018) conceptualised and implemented the first RRI monitoring system in Europe. The recently started SUPER_MoRRI project builds upon and continues the work of MoRRI, ensuring sustained data collection, curation, further assessment and refinement of the MoRRI indicators. EU-28(-27) data will be complemented by monitoring data from selected non-EU countries. SUPER_MoRRI is funded under SwafS-21-2018 - Advancing the Monitoring of the Evolution and Benefits of Responsible Research and Innovation. See <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/824671>.

	GE4	Dissimilarity Index	SHE figure	medium
	GE5	Share of RDI agents with policies to promote gender in research and innovation	primary	high
	GE6	Glass Ceiling Index	SHE figure	medium
	GE7	Gender Pay Gap	Eurostat	low
	GE8	Share of female heads of RDI agents	primary	high
	GE9	Share of gender-balanced recruitment committees at RDI agents	primary	high
	GE10	Share of female inventors and authors	WoS/Patstat	medium
Science Literacy and Science Education	SLSE1	Societal aspects in Science curricula for 15-18 year old students	primary	low
	SLSE2	RRI related training at HEI's	primary	low
	SLSE3	Science communication culture	primary	low
	SLSE4	Citizen science activities in RDI agents	primary	high
Public engagement	PE1	Models of public involvement in RDI decision making	Eurobarometer	high
	PE2	Policy oriented engagement with research and innovation	Eurobarometer	high
	PE3	Citizen preferences for active participation in RDI decision making	Eurobarometer	medium
	PE4	Active information search about controversial technology	Eurobarometer	high
	PE5	Public engagement performance mechanisms at the level of RDI agents	Primary	high
	PE7	Embedment of public engagement activities in the funding structure of key public funding agencies	Primary	very high
	PE8	Public engagement elements as evaluative criteria in research proposal evaluations	Primary	very high
	PE9	Research and innovation democratisation index	Primary	high
	PE10	National infrastructure for involvement of citizens and societal actors in research and innovation	Primary	high
Open access	OA1	Open access literature	WoS/Unpaywall	low
	OA3	Social media outreach/take up of open access literature	WoS altmetric.com	low
	OA4	Public perception of open access	Primary	low
	OA5	Funder mandates	Primary	low
	OA6	RDI actors support structures for researchers as regards incentives and barriers for data sharing	Primary	medium
Ethics	E1a	Ethics at the level of RDI agents	Primary	high

	E1b	Ethics at the level of RDI agents (composite indicator)	Primary	high
	E2	National Ethics Committees index	Primary	high
	E3a	Research-funding organisations index	Primary	high
	E3b	Research-funding organisations index (composite indicator)	Primary	high
Governance	GOV1	Use of science in policymaking	WoS altmetric.com	medium
	GOV2	RRI-related governance mechanisms within RFOs and RDI agents	Primary	medium
	GOV3	RRI-related governance mechanisms within RFOs and RDI agents – composite index	Primary	medium

Table 4: MoRRI Indicators relevant to the PRO-Ethics project

6. References

- Arnstein, S.R. (1969): A Ladder of Citizen Participation. *Journal of the American Institute of Planners*, 35(4): 216–224. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01944366908977225>
- Brest, P. (2010): The Power of Theories of Change. Stanford Social Innovation Review. Spring. https://ssir.org/articles/entry/the_power_of_theories_of_change
- Edler, J., Berger, M., Dinges, M., Gök, A. (2012): The Practice of Evaluation in Innovation Policy in Europe. *Research Evaluation*, 21(3): 167-182. <https://doi.org/10.1093/reseval/rvs014>
- European Commission (2018a): Monitoring the evolution and benefits of responsible Research and Innovation. Brussels <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/d7d917da-c13b-11e8-9893-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>
- European Commission (2018b): Monitoring the evolution and benefits of responsible Research and Innovation – the Indicators report. Brussels <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/2c5a0fb6-c070-11e8-9893-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-search>
- Kohlweg, K. (2019): Evaluation Standards for Research, Technology and Innovation Policy. fteval – Austrian Platform for Research and Technology Policy Evaluation. Vienna. <https://repository.fteval.at/387/>
- OECD DAC (2009): Glossary of Key Terms in Evaluation and Results Based Management. <https://www.oecd.org/dac/evaluation/dcdndep/43184177.pdf>
- Prainsack, B. (2014): The Powers of Participatory Medicine. *PLoS Biol*, 12(4): e1001837. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.1001837>
- Schaefer, T. & Kieslinger, B. (2016): Supporting emerging forms of citizen science: A plea for diversity, creativity and social innovation. *Journal of Science Communication*, 15(02). <https://doi.org/10.22323/2.15020402>
- Scot, J. & Steinmueller, E. (2018): Three frames for innovation policy: R&D, systems of innovation and transformative change. *Research Policy*, 47(9) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2018.08.011>
- Wiggins, A. & Crowston, K. (2011): From Conservation to Crowdsourcing: A Typology of Citizen Science. *Proceedings of the Forty-fourth Hawai'i International Conference on System Science (HICSS-44)*. <https://crowston.syr.edu/sites/crowston.syr.edu/files/hicss-44.pdf>
- Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. (2016): The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

List of Figures and Tables

Figure 1: Example of a Theory of Change	11
Figure 2: Evaluation Plan	13
Figure 3: Four dimensions	14
Table 1: Evaluation questions and indicators.....	15
Table 2: Outputs and Outcomes at various levels.....	20
Table 3: Suggestions for Monitoring data.....	21

